

RI-VIS Website Setup

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Delivery date (actual)	31/07/19
Description of deliverable	Develop and maintain a website for information dissemination and project documentation. P1 will set up a website that will serve as a single-entry point for information regarding the project, including documentation, events, news. A confidential internal area accessible for the internal dissemination of key information and communication tools will be provided alongside the open external site for all public information and external dissemination. The website will be an important vehicle for ensuring high visibility for the joint activities of the consortium and participant stakeholders and to further raise the profile of European RIs, their capabilities and the access routes to their services. It will integrate the activities, events and outcomes of the other work packages in one central place with single access.

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Executive Summary

The RI-VIS website is available at <https://ri-vis.eu> and is built within the ARIA Network framework. The website has the capability to integrate with ease into other ARIA features including the tools improved and developed through work package 4. The website can also provide a platform for open calls which could be used by other work packages. Content such as news posts, event listings, job adverts, and document downloads can be added via dedicated objects. Pages within the website are editable via a content management system with a drag-and-drop interface and customisable content blocks.

The website is the core point of information for many external users to interact with us and is therefore a key dissemination tool. The styling of the website is designed to complement other project materials to ensure a distinctive, coherent and recognisable visual identity for the project.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

RI-VIS works to increase the visibility of Research Infrastructures. A key aspect of this is communication and dissemination activities. A project-specific website provides a public window to the project and is where many users may first come into contact with the project, e.g. finding the RI-VIS website via a search engine. The website can also provide a wealth of additional information to users directed to it after engaging with us through other communication materials and activities such as social media, printed materials, and meeting project representatives at events. The website itself is a useful tool for dissemination, and also for communication as visitors to the website are able to connect with RI-VIS project team via a number of methods.

A secondary purpose of the website is to provide a secure space for sharing internal project materials. As such the website has the ability to restrict access to certain areas, only to logged in users who have been manually approved.

The RI-VIS website was created on the 4th February and formerly launched on the 7th February in a temporary form. The website was renewed following the creation of the project logo on the 1st May.

The website will continue to extend to meet the needs of the project as it evolves including the creation of new website content, and structural reorganisation informed by community feedback and web analytics.

Description of work

RI-VIS ARIA Network

The RI-VIS website was created within the ARIA network framework. ARIA is a suite of cloud services developed by Instruct-ERIC [1]. ARIA is an acronym for Access to Research Infrastructure Administration. ARIA features can be divided into themes of: Management of Infrastructure Access including submission and peer review of proposals and call applications; Management of research facilities including instrument booking calendars, management of remote or physical project shifts; Management of communities including content management and communication tools, document storage and sharing. RI-VIS makes use of the network functionality to create objects in ARIA such as news items, events, job listings, webpages, documents, forums, call applications, in a community run group. Access to network content management is restricted to network administrators who can assign edit permissions to users or user groups for individual objects. News items, events, and job listings are always publicly accessible via the front-end webpages; however, network pages, documents and forums can have customisable access levels, enabling designated ARIA users or groups to access the content.

Styling

In March 2019 a competition was held to invite designs for the RI-VIS project logo. The winning design, selected on 1st May 2019, used the colours blue, white and grey for two versions of the logo, blue background with white images and text, and transparent background with blue images and blue text with grey strapline. The primary colour for the website was derived from the blue of the winning logo, and white and grey form secondary colours. The logo variant with the blue background inspired a blue top menu bar with navigation links. The rest of the page background is white, including the currently selected menu link. The look and feel of the website matches document and presentation templates, and publicity materials for the project so that everything has a coherent and recognisable visual identity.

Website structure

The website homepage gives a brief introduction to the project and live feeds of the @RI_VIS_eu official twitter account [1] and RI-VIS news and events. The inclusion of live content ensures that the homepage content is fresh and up-to-date.

Figure 1: RI-VIS homepage showing summary information about the project and live feeds for twitter, news and events.

Navigation around the website is performed primarily through the header menu, and links in the footer. The header menu shows key menu links along the top blue bar and is annotated in Figure 2. The currently selected link is shown in white. On the right-hand side a green button allows the user to login or logout from the site. Users who are not logged in, or who are logged in but not a member of the RI-VIS network in ARIA will also see the “Join Network” button. Some main menu links also have submenu items. The presence of submenus is indicated by a downward pointing triangle to indicate to users that there is more to see.

Figure 2: Intuitive menu navigation using website header with context dependent login/logout and Join network buttons.

The footer has two elements to it and is shown in Figure 3. The first element is the website footer which contains quick links to the RI-VIS privacy policy, and the acknowledgement statement for the project. Beneath the website footer is the ARIA bar. The ARIA bar can also be found on other ARIA websites such as <https://instruct-eric.eu> and is for administration. The button in the centre of the bar links to the administration panel of ARIA where administrative actions can be performed. The other button on the right-hand side marked “Edit Page” appears only to users who are logged in and have permission to edit the currently displayed page. Page edit permissions can be managed in the administration panel.

Figure 3: Website footer and ARIA administration bar found at the bottom of the webpage. If you are authorised to edit a particular page the "Edit Page" button appears and switches the interface to editing mode on the current page.

A visualisation of the sitemap is given in Figure 4. This map shows the content organised under the navigation menu headings and footer links.

Figure 4: RI-VIS sitemap July 2019. A full list of content is given in Appendix 1: Current website content.

Access control

Authentication is currently provided by the ARIA AAI, which allows users to either log in with institutional credentials through the eduGAIN interfederation [3], Umbrella ID [4], or through creating an account with ARIA’s own IdP. Identities from multiple sources can be linked together into a single ARIA account.

Figure 5: Non-members can request to join the network. Their requests will be approved or rejected by the network administrators.

Once registered in ARIA, users can apply to join the RI-VIS network. There is a link to join on the right-hand side of the navigation menu of the website displayed to all users who are not logged in, or are not a member of the network. By following this link ARIA users can request network membership. Membership requests are managed by network administrators who are designated members of the RI-VIS project consortium using the interface shown in Figure 5.

There are two classes of content on the RI-VIS website: public content which is can be accessed by anyone without login or registration; and restricted content which requires authentication of a user and authorisation for that particular user to access the content. Restricted content can have completely customisable permissions. One or more individual ARIA users or user groups can be added as “owners” of content and “accessors” of content. Owners are able to modify the content whereas accessors can see and interact with the content, but not modify it unless they are also an owner. User groups in ARIA can be manually curated or populated dynamically according to a rule such as “members of the RI-VIS network”. The dynamic group of network members enables convenient internal content sharing.

Website content

News

This is a space for any news posts related to the project. Within the news area Work Package 1 has also started a series of “RI-VIS Spotlights” to showcase initiatives in individual research infrastructures which fit the core themes of the RI-VIS project e.g. examples of forging partnerships, outreach initiatives, and internationalisation. These examples provide fresh content and also provide best practice examples and inspiration for other RIs and stakeholders.

Events

All events organised by RI-VIS, and all events relevant to RI-VIS or where members of the RI-VIS community are attending representing RI-VIS should be added to the events list. Each event has a designated contact person with an ARIA account. Where the contact person does not have an ARIA account, a proxy is added from the RI-VIS community. The name of the contact person is then displayed on the event page so that by clicking on the name any visitor will be able to send an email

to them via a secure form which does not expose their email address. The event location if given will display as a pin on a map.

Documents

Documents can be organised into folders, and folders can be nested, similar to a desktop filesystem. Users can browse the filesystem using the folder list on the left-hand side of the document page shown in Figure 6. Documents in a selected folder are shown in the table on the right-hand side of the page. Users with the permission to access a relevant document will be presented with a link where they can download it. The document area provides a space to store finalised versions of documents and is useful for providing reference documents for download e.g. templates, accepted meeting minutes and publications. The RI-VIS consortium currently makes use of Microsoft SharePoint online for collaborative editing on working/in-progress documents. Due to the access control provided by ARIA the documents uploaded, and document folders created, can be shared openly, or in a restricted manner, as required.

Figure 6: RI-VIS document gallery showing files and folders accessible to a logged in network member. A selected subset of these files are available for public access.

Policies

Visitors to the RI-VIS project, and members of the RI-VIS network are covered by the RI-VIS privacy policy. A link to the privacy policy can be found in the website footer for convenience.

Synergies with activities in other work packages

Work package 4 provided a webinar, broadcast on 28th June 2019, to detail how aria functionality could be used for communities with a particular focus on the RI-VIS project website and its implementation in ARIA. The full webinar can be watched online [5].

Work package 4 is also working to develop and improve the ARIA platform to accommodate the needs of RIs and stakeholders. This work will be presented in a future deliverable D4.1. New functionality established within ARIA will be easily and even automatically integrated with the RI-VIS website.

Within the RI-VIS network, calls can be created to manage submission and evaluation of applications for a specified topic. This functionality has already been used to manage the logo competition but could potentially be used by other work packages in RI-VIS e.g. work package 5 for the staff mobility program call. ARIA also provides a survey tool with applied RI-VIS styling which could be used by work packages for data collection and feedback.

Conclusion/Next steps

The immediate next steps are to create more content for the website and to drive traffic to the website by publicising it through dissemination channels. As more results are created in the RI-VIS work packages, these will be shared and promoted via the website. In particular, development of the sections for the individual work packages will be updated as a result of activity within the work packages.

Metrics will be collected on website usage and used to inform the navigation of the website and pages of particular relevance to our website visitors.

References

- [1] Instruct-ERIC, “ARIA,” [Online]. Available: <http://aria.instruct-eric.eu/>.
- [2] “RI-VIS Twitter Profile,” [Online]. Available: https://twitter.com/RI_VIS_eu.
- [3] GÉANT, [Online]. Available: <https://edugain.org/>.
- [4] UMBRELLA. [Online]. Available: <https://www.umbrellaid.org/>.
- [5] N. Haley, “RI-VIS Webinar: Using ARIA for RI-VIS networks, forums, content and more,” 28 06 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/webinars/using-aria-for-rivis-networks-forums-content-and-more>.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Current website content

Content type	Title	URL
pages	home	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/home
pages	Work Packages	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/work-packages
pages	Work Package 1: Management and Dissemination	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/work-package-1-management-and-dissemination
pages	Work Package 2: Mapping and enabling new partnerships	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/work-package-2-mapping-and-enabling-new-partnerships
pages	Work Package 3: Outreach Events	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/work-package-3-outreach-events
pages	Work Package 4: International Cooperation	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/work-package-4-international-cooperation
pages	Work Package 5: Long-term sustainability of RIs	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/work-package-5-longterm-sustainability-of-ris
pages	Project Team	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/project-team
pages	Partners	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/partners
pages	Governance	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/governance
link	Documents	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents
documents	RI-VIS	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents/191
documents	Deliverables and Milestones	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents/220
documents	Logos	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents/202
documents	MASTER blue background	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents/205
documents	Transparent for light background	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents/211
documents	Transparent for dark background	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents/208
documents	RI-VIS Meetings	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents/194
documents	Kick-off	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents/214
documents	Steering Group	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/documents/199
pages	Webinars	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/webinars

pages	Using ARIA for RI-VIS: Networks, forums, content and more	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/webinars/using-aria-for-rivis-networks-forums-content-and-more
link	News	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/news
news	RI-VIS Logo Competition Winner	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/news/ri-vis-logo-competition-winner
news	RI-VIS project officially launched	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/news/ri-vis-project-officially-launched
news	RI-VIS Spotlight on Instruct-ERIC cooperation with Latin America	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/news/ri-vis-spotlight-on-instruct-eric-cooperation-with-latin-america
link	Events	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events
events	1st RI-VIS Steering Group Meeting	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/1st-ri-vis-steering-group-meeting
events	2nd RI-VIS Steering Group Meeting	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/2nd-ri-vis-steering-group-meeting
events	CatRIS First Workshop	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/catris-first-workshop
events	CatRIS Focus group on testing and validation of the concept of CatRIS, the Catalogue of Research Infrastructure Services	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/catris-focus-group-on-testing-and-validation-of-the-concept-of-catris-the-catalogue-of-research-infr
events	Instruct Biennial Structural Biology Conference 2019	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/instruct-biennial-structural-biology-conference-2019
events	MERIL2 Final Conference	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/meril2-final-conference
events	RI-VIS at AAAS meeting	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/ri-vis-at-aaas-meeting
events	RI-VIS kick off meeting	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/ri-vis-kick-off-meeting
events	RI-VIS Work Package 5 Workshop#1 - Communication Toolkit	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/ri-vis-work-package-5-workshop1---communication-toolkit
events	RI-VIS WP3 Telco	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/ri-vis-wp3-telco
events	Webinar: Using ARIA for RI-VIS - Networks, forums, content and more	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/webinar-using-aria-for-ri-vis---networks-forums-content-and-more
pages	Connect	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/connect
forums	RI-VIS	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/forums
pages	Contact	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/contact
link	Jobs	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/jobs
jobs	Communication Officer position at Euro-Argo ERIC	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/jobs/communication-officer-position-at-euro-argo-eric
link	Join Network	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/join
pages	Privacy Policy	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/privacy-policy
calls	RI-VIS project logo competition	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/calls/ri-vis-project-logo-competition